

CHEMISTRY

MODIFICATIONS OF ZSM-5 ZEOLITE WITH TUNGSTEN AND YTTERBIUM ON ITS CATALYTIC PROPERTIES FOR THE CONVERSION OF NATURAL GAS

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Abstract

The joint promoting effect of tungsten and ytterbium on the catalytic properties of high silica zeolite type ZSM-5 in the process of conversion of natural gas into aromatic hydrocarbons was studied. It has been shown that the addition of Yb to W-containing zeolite leads to a redistribution of acid sites and an increase in the activity and selectivity of the catalyst in the formation of aromatic hydrocarbons from natural gas components. It has been established that in the temperature range 700 - 750°C the maximum number of aromatic hydrocarbons (25.6 - 28.1 wt. %) with a selectivity of 79.6 - 80.8 is formed on catalysts 1.5% Yb - 4% W/HZSM.

Keywords: high silica zeolite type ZSM-5, conversion, natural gas, aromatic hydrocarbons, tungsten, and ytterbium.

Introduction

Aromatic hydrocarbons, the most important raw materials of the petrochemical industry, are obtained mainly through the processes of pyrolysis, alkylation, reforming, and hydro processing of petroleum fractions. However, limited oil reserves force us to look for other hydrocarbon raw materials. One of the solutions to the problem of finding alternative raw materials for obtaining gaseous hydrocarbons for processing. Therefore, the development of catalytic gas processing with the most comprehensive and rational use of all components included in natural and associated gases is a pressing task today [1, p. 13794-13797] [5, p. 1-2].

The process of aromatization of lower C₂-C₄ alkanes occurs in the presence of various catalytic systems, among which high-silica zeolites of the ZSM-5 type are considered more effective; modification of groups II, III and VIII have high activity and selectivity in the aromatization of lower C₂-C₄ alkanes [8, p. 145-149]. Currently, extensive research is being carried out on the development of catalytic systems capable of converting methane, the main component of natural gas, into benzene in one stage under non-oxidizing conditions with high selectivity [2, p. 24910 -24918] [5, p. 1-2].

Zeolites of the ZSM-5 type, modified with molybdenum, zinc, zirconium and gallium, exhibit fairly high activity in the dehydroaromatization of methane [3, p. 388 - 392] [8, p. 145 -149]. Therefore, it is of undoubted interest to study the joint promoting effect of tungsten and ytterbium on the acidic and catalytic properties of high-silica zeolite type ZSM-5 in the process of converting natural gas components into aromatic hydrocarbons. The purpose of this work was to study the joint promoting effect of tungsten and ytterbium on the catalytic properties of ZSM-5 type zeolite during the conversion of natural gas into aromatic hydrocarbons.

Experimental part

For the study, we used high silica zeolite type ZSM-5 with a molar ratio of SiO₂/Al₂O₃ = 33, which

was converted into the NH₄ form by ion exchange according to the method described in [3, p. 388 - 392]. The H-form of zeolite was obtained by thermal decomposition of the NH₄-form at 550°C for 4 hours. Catalysts, modification 4.0 wt. % tungsten and 0.3 - 2.0 wt. % of ytterbium was obtained by impregnating the HZSM with ammonium para-tungstate (NH₄/W₇O₂₄ * 4H₂O) and a solution of ytterbium nitrate, followed by drying in air for 16 hours, then 4 hours in an oven at 110°C and finally baking in a muffle furnace at 550°C for 4 hours. The acid properties of modified zeolites were studied by the thermal desorption of ammonia method.

Results

Unmodified HZSM-5 exhibits low catalytic activity in the conversion of natural gas in the temperature range 660 - 750°C, which is 13.5 - 14.3% and the yield of aromatic hydrocarbons is 5.3 - 6.4% (Table 1). The introduction of 4.0% W into HZSM-5 leads to an increase in the activity and selectivity of the catalyst. As the process temperature increases, the conversion of natural gas and selectivity for aromatic hydrocarbons increases. At a temperature of 750°C on W-containing zeolite, the conversion of natural gas reaches 26.9% with a yield of aromatic hydrocarbons equal to 21.1%. It should be noted that when modifying HZSM-5 with tungsten, a sharp increase in selectivity for aromatic hydrocarbons occurs throughout the entire temperature range. Thus, in the studied temperature range on HZSM and HZSM-5 4.0% W, the selectivity for aromatic hydrocarbons is 36.5-46.4% and 69.8-78.3%, respectively. The main liquid products are benzene and naphthalene, the concentration of which significantly increases the concentration of water and decreases the number of alkanes and alkenes. The addition of a small amount of ytterbium (0.3%) to W-containing zeolite leads to an increase in the conversion of natural gas and the yield of aromatic hydrocarbons. At a temperature of 700° C, the yield of aromatic hydrocarbons increases from 13.9% to 20.8%. With an increase in the ytterbium concentration in HZSM to 1.5%, a further increase in the conversion of natural gas and the yield of aromatic

hydrocarbons is observed. On samples containing 1.0 - 1.5% ytterbium at a temperature of 750 °C, the yield of aromatic hydrocarbons is 14.1 and 16.6% with selectivity for aromatic hydrocarbons equal to 79.7 - 80.6%. However, further increasing the ytterbium concentration on the 4.0% W/HZSM sample reduces the activity

and selectivity of the catalyst. On a sample of 2.0% ytterbium - 4.0% W/HZSM in the temperature range 700 - 750 °C, the yield of aromatic hydrocarbons is 18.6 - 20.4% with a selectivity of 77.1 - 77.2%. The concentration of benzene and naphthalene in liquid products is significantly reduced.

Table 1.

Effect of different catalysts and operating conditions on the yields

T, °C	X, %								Exit Aromatic %	S _{aro}
		H ₂	C ₂ - C ₄ alkanes	C ₂ - C ₄ alkenes	C ₆ H ₆	C ₇ H ₈	C ₁₀ H ₈	C ₁₁ - C ₁₂		
HZSM										
650	13.90	1.7	86.1	7.1	2.97	0.71	0.74	0.68	5.1	36.5
700	14.3	1.68	86.3	5.78	3.28	0.57	1.56	0.99	6.4	44.4
750	13.5	1.54	86.8	5.6	3.16	0.42	1.96	0.66	6.2	46.4
4% W/HZSM										
650	12.3	1.5	87.7	2.2	4.5	0.2	3.7	0.1	8.6	69.8
700	18.5	2.7	81.5	1.9	6.3	0.2	7.4	0.2	13.9	75.2
750	26.9	4.3	73.1	1.5	11.6	0.1	9.2	0.2	21.1	78.3
0.3% Yb - 4% W/HZSM										
650	14.5	1.95	85.5	1.6	4.9	0.2	5.7	0.2	11.0	75.8
700	26.1	4.22	73.9	1.3	9.7	0.2	10.4	0.3	20.5	78.5
750	30.5	5.43	69.5	1.3	12.4	0.1	11.0	0.4	24.1	78.0
1% Yb - 4% W/HZSM										
700	31.0	5.0	69.0	1.25	11.5	0.18	12.9	0.47	24.8	80.3
750	32.8	5.5	67.2	1.18	12.2	0.17	13.	0.54	26.6	79.7
1.5% Yb - 4% W/HZSM										
650	21.6	3.05	78.4	2.1	6.5	0.21	9.2	0.4	16.4	75.9
700	31.0	4.97	68.4	1.23	11.6	0.17	13.0	0.5	25.4	80.6
750	33.0	5.49	67.0	1.15	12.5	0.15	13.1	0.6	26.3	79.5

Thus, based on the data obtained, we can conclude that the highest activity in relation to the formation of aromatic hydrocarbons from natural gas is found in zeolite catalysts containing 1.0 - 1.5% Yb and 4.0% W.

Differences in the activity of the original and modified zeolites in the conversion of natural gas into aromatic hydrocarbons are associated with the nature of their active sites, that is, the concentration and strength of the acid sites. The results of studies of the acidic properties of the synthesized catalyst samples are given in Table 2. The H-form of zeolite has the greatest strength and concentration of acid sites.

When 4% tungsten is introduced into the zeolite, a decrease in the strength and concentration of acid sites of both types is observed by almost 2 times. The additional introduction Yb into the catalyst in an amount of 0.3% unto 4.0% W/HZSM leads to an increase in the strength and concentration of acid sites. With an increase in the Yb content in zeolite to 1.5%, the strength

and concentration of weak acid sites decreases slightly, while the strength and concentration of acid sites increases. For the 1.5% Yb - 4%W/HZSM sample, the concentration of strong acid sites is 240 μmol/g, which is 36 μmol/g higher than for the 4%W/HZSM catalyst. With a further increase in the amount of administered lanthanum to 2%, a decrease in the strength and concentration of centers of both types is observed. Thus, the modification of zeolite W and Yb leads to a redistribution of its acid centers throughout the salt and the formation of new active centers, which include modifier elements. Changing the ratio of acid sites on their catalytic properties during the conversion of natural gas. To obtain an effective catalyst for the conversion of natural gas into aromatic hydrocarbons, a certain combination of weak and strong acid sites is required in the catalyst, which is achieved by regulating the number of modifiers in the catalytic system.

Table 2.

The results of the acidic properties of the synthesized catalyst samples

Zeolites	Max temperature		Concentration	
	T ₁ (K)	T ₂	C ₁	C ₂
HZSM	471	688	520	542
4% W/HZSM	462	661	356	304
0.3% Yb - 4% W/HZSM	467	681	332	262
1% Yb - 4% W/HZSM	463	687	317	247
1.5% Yb - 4% W/HZSM	458	680	309	221
2% Yb - 4% W/HZSM	443	668	284	194

References

1. Cao, Z., Jiang, H., Luo, H., Baumann, S., Meulenberg, W. A., Abmann, J., Mleczko, L., Liu, Y., & Caro, J. (2013). Natural gas to fuels and chemicals: Improved methane aromatization in an Oxygen-Permeable Membrane reactor. *Angewandte Chemie*, 52(51), 13794–13797. <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.201307935>
2. Gabrienko AA, Arzumanov SS, Luzgin MV, Stepanov AG, Parmon VN. Methane activation on Zn²⁺-exchanged ZSM-5 zeolites: the effect of molecular oxygen addition. *J Physical Chem C*, 119 (44) (2015): 24910–24918
3. Ганбарова. Е.А., Алиев Т.А., Мамедов С.Э., Махмудова Н.И. Превращение природного газа на высококремнеземном цеолите типа ЦВМ, модифицированного нанопорошками циркония и молибдена. // Проблемы химии - 2015. - No 4 - с. 388 – 392.
4. Petkovic LM, Ginosar DM. Comparison of two preparation methods on catalytic activity and selectivity of Ru-Mo/HZSM5 for methane dehydroaromatization. *J Fuels*, 7 (2014).
5. Huang, K., & Maravelias, C. T. (2019). Synthesis and analysis of nonoxidative methane aromatization strategies. *Energy Technology*, 8(8). <https://doi.org/10.1002/ente.201900650>
6. Samanta A, Bai X, Robinson B, Chen H, Hu J., Conversion of light alkane to value-added chemicals over ZSM-5/metal promoted catalysts. *Indus Engg Chem Research* 2017.
7. Spivey JJ, Hutchings G., Catalytic aromatization of methane. *Chem Soc’y Revs*, 43 (3) (2014): 792–803.
8. Zhang Y., Wang D., Fei J. X. Z. Effect of preparation conditions on methane aromatization performance of Mo/HZSM-5 and Mo-Cu/HZSM-5 catalysts // *Journal of Natural Gas Chemistry* – 2003. – V. 12 – P. 145 - 149